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**UNCOVERING INTRAUTERINE PATHOLOGY:
HYSTEROSCOPIC FINDINGS AMONG INFERTILE WOMEN
AT A NIGERIAN TERTIARY HOSPITAL**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hysteroscopy enables direct visualization of the uterine cavity using a hysteroscope and has transformed the diagnosis and management of intrauterine pathology in modern gynaecology. However, the World Health Organization recommends its use mainly after failed in-vitro fertilization or when other investigations, such as ultrasonography or hysterosalpingography, indicate intrauterine abnormalities. Uterine pathology remains a significant factor that can adversely affect fertility outcomes in both natural conception and assisted reproductive techniques.

Aim: To evaluate the role of Hysteroscopy in diagnosing the abnormalities of the uterine cavity among female being evaluated for infertility at FMC, Jabi

Study Design: It was a descriptive retrospective study which was carried out on females being evaluated for infertility at FMC, Jabi between 1st January 2021 and 31st December 2021.

Results: The mean age was 40.2 ± 7.8 years. The highest percentage of the included cases were in the age group between 40-49 years (53.1%) followed by those age between 30-39 years (34.3%). Secondary infertility was the major type of infertility seen in 81.3%. Normal hysteroscopic findings were reported in 15.6% of women. The other 84.4% were with abnormal hysteroscopy. The most common reported hysteroscopic abnormality was intrauterine adhesions 34.4% followed by cervical stenosis 21.8%.

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Conclusion: Majority of the women who were evaluated for infertility had an abnormal finding, hence routine diagnostic hysteroscopy should be part of the infertility workup in both primary and secondary infertility.

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is a disorder of the reproductive system characterized by the inability to achieve a clinical pregnancy after at least 12 months of regular, unprotected sexual intercourse¹. Globally, an estimated 72.4 million women are affected, with approximately 40.5 million actively seeking fertility treatment¹. In contemporary clinical practice, baseline hysteroscopy is increasingly recommended before advanced assisted reproductive procedures such as in vitro fertilization and embryo transfer, particularly following previous failed attempts^{1,2}. Diagnostic and operative hysteroscopy plays a pivotal role in the evaluation of infertility and is regarded as the gold standard for assessing the uterine cavity, as it allows direct visualization of the endometrium and intrauterine architecture.

Both congenital and acquired uterine abnormalities have been identified as significant contributors to infertility, accounting for approximately 10–15% of cases among couples seeking treatment². Evaluation of the uterine cavity may be undertaken using transvaginal ultrasonography, hysterosalpingography (HSG), sonohysterography, or hysteroscopy³. Although the World Health Organization recommends HSG as the primary investigation in infertile women due to its ability to assess tubal patency²⁻⁵, hysteroscopy offers distinct advantages, including assessment of cavity accessibility for insemination or embryo transfer and direct visualization of the endometrial surface and cavity contour. Consequently, hysteroscopy has been associated with improved clinical pregnancy and live birth rates among women undergoing IVF⁵⁻⁷.

Despite its proven benefits, hysteroscopy remains underutilized in Nigeria, where the prevalence of intrauterine adhesions is relatively high⁸⁻⁹. Incorporating hysteroscopy into routine infertility evaluation is therefore desirable but requires specialized training and infrastructural investment, posing significant financial challenges in resource-limited settings^{9,10}. Accordingly, careful clinical assessment to identify women at high risk of intrauterine pathology is essential to optimize infertility management in such environments.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

It was a descriptive retrospective study of women who were evaluated for infertility with hysteroscopy in Federal Medical Centre, Jabi over a year. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institution's Ethics and Research Committee prior to the commencement of the study. A list of all women that were evaluated for infertility with hysteroscopy from the 1st of January 2021 to 31st of December 2021 was compiled from the gynaecological clinic and theatre records, and the case notes were retrieved from the Medical Records Department of the hospital. Folder retrieval was 100%. Relevant data were extracted and entered into a proforma. The data was coded and entered into a spread sheet and analysed using SPSS for windows 25.0 version.

RESULTS:

The mean age was 40.2 ± 6.6 years. The highest percentage of the included cases were in the age group between 40-49 years (53.1%) followed by those aged between 30-39 years (34.3%).

Secondary infertility was the major type of infertility seen in 81.3%. Normal hysteroscopic findings were reported in 15.6% of women. The other 84.4% were with abnormal hysteroscopy. The most common reported hysteroscopic abnormality was intrauterine adhesions 34.4% followed by cervical stenosis 21.8%.

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics.

Age	Frequency	%
20 – 29	2	6.3
30 – 39	11	34.3
40 – 49	17	53.1
MARITAL STATUS		
Single	-	-
Married	32	32
RELIGION		
Christian	28	87.5
Islam	4	12.5
EDUCATIONAL STATUS		
Primary	-	-
Secondary	-	-
Tertiary	32	32

Most of the women were aged between 40-49 years, married. Christian with tertiary level of education

Table 2: Hysteroscopic findings.

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Normal	5	15.6
Endometrial polyp	2	6.3
Cervical polyp	-	-
Uterine fibroids	6	18.8
Intrauterine adhesions	11	34.4
Uterine septum	-	-
Cervical stenosis	7	21.8
Endometrial hyperplasia	1	3.1
Total	32	100

Normal hysteroscopic findings were reported in 15.6% of women. The other 84.4% were with abnormal hysteroscopy. The most common reported hysteroscopic abnormality was intrauterine adhesions 34.4% followed by cervical stenosis 21.8%.

DISCUSSION

Hysteroscopy plays a crucial role in the evaluation of infertility by identifying intrauterine abnormalities that may impair embryo implantation and by facilitating interventions aimed at restoring normal endometrial anatomy. Its introduction into modern gynecological practice has markedly improved the visualization and management of intrauterine pathology. In the present study, the mean age of participants was 40.2 ± 6.6 years, which is comparable to findings from Port Harcourt reported by Emeka Ray-Offor et al¹, but higher than values reported in similar studies conducted elsewhere in Nigeria⁹ and Egypt¹¹.

Most women evaluated were within the 40–49-year age group, consistent with findings from an Indian study where infertility evaluation was more common among women of advanced reproductive age¹². This contrasts with observations by Kabeil¹¹. The predominance of older women may reflect delayed childbearing related to educational and career pursuits. Notably, all participants had attained tertiary education, which may have contributed both to delayed fertility and increased health-seeking behavior.

Secondary infertility was more prevalent than primary infertility, accounting for 81.3% of cases. This finding aligns with reports by Jesmine et al² and Ugboaja et al¹³ but differs from studies by Abd El-Nasser⁵ and Sahu et al¹². The higher rate of secondary infertility associated with abnormal hysteroscopic findings may be attributed to intrauterine adhesions, which were the most frequently observed pathology. These adhesions often result from uterine trauma following unsafe or repeated dilatation and curettage procedures, as well as post-infectious complications¹³. Additional risk factors include excessive curettage for abortion or postpartum hemorrhage, complicated caesarean section, and myomectomy.

A normal uterine cavity was observed in 15.6% of participants, comparable to findings by Jesmine et al² and Ugboaja et al¹³, but lower than rates reported by Abd El-Nasser⁵ and Sahu et al¹². Abnormal hysteroscopic findings were detected in 84.4% of cases, similar to reports from Eastern Nigeria¹³. Intrauterine adhesions were the most common abnormality, present in 34.4% of cases, consistent with previous studies from Nigeria^{10, 14, 15} and India¹⁶. These adhesions result from damage to the basal layer of the endometrium due to trauma or infection, leading to endometrial scarring and partial or complete obliteration of the uterine cavity¹⁰. The clinical consequences include subfertility, recurrent pregnancy loss, abnormal placentation, and an increased risk of ectopic pregnancy. Other abnormalities identified were cervical stenosis

(21.8%), uterine fibroids (18.8%), endometrial polyps (6.3%), and endometrial hyperplasia (3.1%).

Overall, these findings underscore the importance of hysteroscopy as a primary investigative modality in the evaluation of female infertility. Direct visualization of the endometrial cavity not only enhances diagnostic accuracy but also guides appropriate therapeutic interventions, thereby potentially improving conception rates within a relatively short period.

CONCLUSION

The prevalence of abnormal findings on hysteroscopy among the studied women was high and comprised mainly of intrauterine adhesions and cervical stenosis. These findings emphasize the need to adopt hysteroscopy in the routine evaluation of female infertility for better outcome.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Idea/Concept: Atemie Gordon, Fetepigi E. Amiete, Ekweani John; Design: Atemie Gordon, Fetepigi E. Amiete, Ekweani John, Sheu T. Medinat; Control/Supervision: Fetepigi E. Amiete, Ekweani John, Sheu T. Medinat, Osayande Augustine; Data Collection and/or Processing: Fetepigi E. Amiete, Ekweani John, Sheu T. Medinat, Osayande Augustine; Analysis and/or Interpretation: Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Awudu S. Tuboulayefa; Literature Review: Atemie Gordon, Fetepigi E. Amiete Atemie Gordon, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong; Writing the Article: Fetepigi E. Amiete; Critical Review: Atemie Gordon, Fetepigi E. Amiete, Ekweani John, Sheu T. Medinat, Osayande Augustine, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Awudu S. Tuboulayefa

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethical committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Jabi.

REFERENCES

1. Emeka Ray-Offor et al. Diagnostic yield and therapeutic outcome of hysteroscopy in women with infertility in a referral clinical setting: a Port Harcourt, Nigeria experience. *Pan African Medical Journal*. 2021;38(155). 10.11604/pamj.2021.38.155.27101
2. Jesmine B, Farzana D, Parveen F, Parveen S. Evaluation of Uterine Cavity by Hysteroscopic Examination in Infertile Women in BSMMU. *BSMMUJ*. 2016; 9 (1): 32-37.
3. Zhu H, Fu J, Lei H, Song Y, Shen L, Huang W. Evaluation of transvaginal sonography in detecting endometrial polyps and the pregnancy outcome following hysteroscopic polypectomy in infertile women. *Experimental and therapeutic medicine*. 2016; 12(2):1196-200.
4. Omidiji OA, Toyobo OO, Adegbola O, Fatade A, Olowoyeye OA. Hysterosalpingography findings in infertility—what has changed over the years? *African health sciences*. 2019; 19(2):1866-74.

5. Abd El-Nasser EMH, Mohammad SEH, Basem RA. Hysteroscopic Findings In Patients with Secondary Infertility. *AIMJ*. 2022; 1 : 108-112.
6. Di Spiezio Sardo A, Di Carlo C, Minozzi S, Spinelli M, Pistotti V, Alviggi C, et al. Efficacy of hysteroscopy in improving reproductive outcomes of infertile couples: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Hum Reprod Update*. 2016; 22(4):479–96.
7. Noa Ndoua C, Ayissi NG , Metogo J, Belinga É , Kasia Onana YB, Mendibi S, et al. Hysteroscopic Features of Endocavitary Lesions at CHRACERH, Cameroon. *Health Sci. Dis.*2018; 19 (4): 61-65.
8. Ajayi A, Biobaku O, Ajayi V, Oyetunji I, Aikhuele H, Afolabi BM. Detection of Intrauterine Lesions by Hysteroscopy among Women with Fertility Challenges in an In-Vitro Fertilization Center in Lagos, Nigeria. *Crit Care Obstet Gynecol*. 2015; 1(1): 8.
9. Ugboaja JO, Blanche CO , Oranu EO , Monago EN , Ogelle OM, Igwegbe AO. Correlates of abnormal hysteroscopy findings among infertile women in Nigeria. *Int. J. Med. Med. Sci*. 2017; 9(11) : 142-147. DOI: 10.5897/IJMMS2017.1335
10. Ugboaja JO, Oguejiofor CB, Ogelle OM. Audit of operative hysteroscopies among infertile women in a resource-poor setting. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 2018;141:57-62.
11. Kabeil EG , Ageez MN , Algergawy AE, and Ahmed Hussein AF. Hysteroscopic Finding in Patients with Secondary Infertility at Tanta University Hospitals. *Journal of Advances in Medicine and Medical Research*.2022; 34(13): 1-11.
12. Sahu L, Tempe A, Gupta S. Hysteroscopic evaluation in infertile patients: a prospective study. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol* 2012;1:1-5.
13. Ugboaja JO, Oguejiofor CB, Igwegbe AO, Oranu EO. Abnormal hysteroscopy findings among a cross section of infertile Nigerian women. *Niger J Clin Pract* 2019;22:9-15.
14. Ajayi A, Biobaku O, Ajayi V, Oyetunji I, Aikhuele H, Afolabi B. Detection of intrauterine lesions by hysteroscopy among women with fertility challenges in an in vitro fertilization center in Lagos, Nigeria. *Crit Care Obstet Gynecol* 2015;1:1. 15.
15. Ajayi AB, Ajayi VD, Kolade CO. Hysteroscopic Findings Among a Cohort of Infertile Nigerian Women Undergoing an IVF Program. Available from: <http://www.nordicalagos.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/Hysteroscopic>.
16. Neerja JK. Role of laparoscopy-hysteroscopy in cases of infertility with pregnancy outcome. *J Indian Med Assoc*. 2014;112:85-6, 88.